

Network Optimization as a Service with Net2Plan

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Abstract—Carrier-grade telecommunication infrastructure must support an ever-increasing traffic volume and dynamicity in operationally-complex networks characterized by multiple domains, multiple technologies and equipment from multiple vendors. At the same time, the advent of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies create transport ecosystems with unprecedented network control and resource dynamicity capabilities. In this context, network optimization is essential to efficiently employ network resources, relying whenever possible on automated procedures and exploiting open application programming interfaces (APIs) inherent of SDN/NFV ecosystems. Automated network optimization procedures on top of network controllers promote a client layer of third-party applications that enable optimization-as-a-service (OaaS) business opportunities. In this paper, we present a network OaaS framework built as an extension of the Net2Plan open-source network planning tool. The proposed framework is based on a classical client-server architecture, and through a REST-based API, holders of network infrastructures (i.e. client role) may request the resolution of a network resource allocation problem through the execution of an algorithmic technique. Thus, third-party players can focus on the development of optimization algorithms (i.e. server role) while potentially providing high-performance computing (HPC) capabilities for their execution. Through the paper, we detail the workflow of the proposed OaaS, illustrate its usage with several use-cases and discuss its applicability in different scenarios.

Keywords— *Network optimization; Optimization as a service; REST API; Software-Defined Networking.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Carrier-grade telecommunication infrastructure must support current and forecasted ever-increasing traffic volume and dynamicity [1]. Operators are forced to upgrade their infrastructure commonly deploying network domains which are characterized as vendor islands of specific technological implementations (e.g. ad-hoc network management systems and/or proprietary control interfaces). This greatly increases operational complexity because managing multi-vendor equipment requires the adaptation of control interfaces just to perform end-to-end (and multi-layer) resource provisioning [2].

At the same time, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies enable the creation of transport ecosystems with unprecedented network control and resource dynamicity capabilities. SDN enables the implementation, from a logically centralized controller, of flexible traffic forwarding rules by switches that behave as simple forwarding devices [3]. NFV permits the

deployment of virtualized network functions (VNFs) as software pieces running in commodity servers [4], replacing bare metal hardware implementing such function. SDN and NFV increase network programmability, control and resource dynamicity because VNFs can be flexibly deployed and jointly exploited with centralized traffic flow policies and (re)configurations.

In this context, network optimization is essential to efficiently employ network resources, relying whenever possible on automated procedures and exploiting open application programming interfaces (APIs) inherent of SDN/NFV ecosystems [5]. Automated network optimization procedures on top of network controllers (or orchestrators) promote a client layer of third-party applications that enable optimization-as-a-service (OaaS) business opportunities [6]. For instance, label-switched path (LSP) computation and allocation in GMPLS-based networks is commonly externalized to a dedicated and specialized Path Computation Element (PCE) [7]. From an industrial perspective, proprietary network optimization tools can provide NVF optimization exploiting interfaces available in open system, e.g. Cisco's Optimization Service for NFV that offers, among the inherent vendor-specific programs, an OpenStack (i.e., open-source) Lifecycle Management support [8].

In this paper, we present an open-source network OaaS framework built as an extension of the Net2Plan [9] open-source network planning tool. The proposed framework is intended to facilitate the prototyping of OaaS systems. Net2Plan-OaaS is based on a classical client-server architecture. The OaaS server will host and expose a catalogue of algorithms to solve a variety of resource allocation problems. Through a REST-based API, clients with the appropriate credentials can manage the catalogue, i.e. uploading algorithm implementations. Then, the REST API permits making use of network optimization algorithms, again, to users with the appropriate permissions. Through the paper, we detail the workflow of the proposed OaaS, illustrate its usage with several use-cases and discuss its applicability in different scenarios.

Net2Plan-OaaS initiative is intended to foster the OaaS business model in which, on the one hand, third-party players can focus on developing and provisioning optimization algorithms while potentially providing high-performance computing (HPC) capabilities for their execution; and on the other hand, holders of network infrastructures may request the resolution of an optimization problem through the execution of an algorithmic technique.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section we first provide a wide contextualization of OaaS frameworks and approaches in the context of cloud computing. Then, we cover works that leverage on OaaS to tackle network optimization problems.

A. OaaS Exploiting Cloud Computing Infrastructure

Within the cloud computing paradigm, the term Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) aims to provide traditional hardware resources as dynamically virtualized entities following the “as a service” approach. IaaS relies on Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) to instantiate, interconnect and manage the life cycle of virtual machine (VM) instances that use the data center computing capabilities, storage facilities and communication services of the data center network. Precisely, VIMs are in charge of providing these services creating/migrating/deleting VM instances, disk images, and the management of the VM network interfaces. OpenStack [10], an open-source option, is positioned as the most popular VIM.

In this context, works in the literature commonly exploit the large amount of computing resources provided by IaaS in cloud computing to execute optimization software. A clear example is [11], in which authors investigate the use of cloud computing for metaheuristic optimization and propose a cost model for the expenses of using virtual resources when providing the so called OaaS. Similarly, Li *et al.* [12] propose cloud-based framework for simulation-based OaaS to enable a flexible and highly parallelizable dynamic decision support for environments that require optimization driven by large amounts of dynamic data. An analysis of several research initiatives and the requirements in the context of OaaS for mathematical and simulation-based optimization can be found in [13]. Works in the literature also address the optimization of services that are executed in cloud environments, leading to service OaaS, which in practice aim to organize, (re)allocate VMs and deploy services on VM cloud infrastructure [14].

In summary, the term “OaaS” encompasses a set of initiatives devoted to exploit the IaaS principle in cloud computing to perform optimization with a variety of objectives, leading to different OaaS flavors.

B. OaaS in SDN/NFV Ecosystems

SDN and NFV enable high levels of network control and resource dynamicity which opens the door to numerous optimization opportunities [6]. Among the use-cases listed in [6], it is worthwhile to recall: optical parameter configurations (e.g. transmission power, amplifier gain, WSS filtering) for WDM (partially) disaggregated networks performed by optimization applications that account on detailed physical-layer models [15]; LSP computation and allocation in GMPLS-based networks by means of a dedicated and specialized PCE through a well-defined interface and PCE protocol (PCEP) [7], and many initiatives in the context of VNF performance and network service optimization both open-source [16] and proprietary [8].

The referred optimization opportunities, although commonly based on open-source frameworks, present a limited applicability because they are defined for narrow scopes.

Fig. 1. Net2Plan-based OaaS general architecture overview, in which XML-based network representations in native Net2Plan files (.n2p) are used by clients to request optimization services.

Nonetheless, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, the proposed Net2Plan-OaaS initiative represent a novel open-source approach devoted to network optimization following an “as a service” approach through a well-defined interface and relying on a currently available large algorithm repository.

III. NET2PLAN OaaS ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we first present the network OaaS architecture based on Net2Plan. Then, we detail the server implementation while describing the REST-based interface definition. Finally, a JAVA-based client implementation is reported.

A. Net2Plan OaaS General Architecture Overview

Fig. 1 illustrates the Net2Plan-based network OaaS architecture, which is based on a classical client–server approach. The interaction between clients and the server is motivated by the need to execute an algorithmic technique to address an optimization problem on a variety of network scenarios that are represented with Net2Plan native files (.n2p). Net2Plan network representations are XML-based abstractions that contain a detailed status of all the characteristics of the network. For instance, optimization services for an IP network, an IP over WDM network, and IT resource allocation (i.e. data center resources) over an IP network are requested by client #1, #2 and #N, respectively. Optimization services can be *algorithms* or *reports*. On the one hand, algorithms consume a network status described as .n2p file as input information and generate a potentially modified (.n2p) network status. For instance, an algorithm may receive a network with unsatisfied demands at the optical layer, representing lightpath requests, and then return the same design with the Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) decision included: the optical wavelength and route assigned to each lightpath. On the other hand, reports analyze (i.e. perform calculations) on a network status (.n2p) and generate human-readable information in HTML format.

B. Network OaaS Server and Interface Definition

The proposed network OaaS server [17] runs on a Tomcat server, an open-source JAVA-based servlet container developed by Apache [18]. Tomcat permits the deployment and execution of JAVA-based applications (.war) and provides multiple functionalities including servlets management, URL mapping and access control.

The following resources compose the REST-based API in the hierarchy illustrated in Fig. 2, while also implementing their associated methods.

/authenticate

1. POST: Authenticates a client by requesting a token to establish a session.

/catalogs

2. POST: Permits to upload a catalog implemented as JAR file and producing a JSON response. The JAR file contains a set of .class files one for each algorithm or report.
3. GET: Generates a JSON response file with the list of all available catalogs with all the algorithms and reports contained in each of them. Therefore, this method returns to the user the extensive list of algorithms and reports available in the repository.

/catalogs/{name}

4. GET: Returns a JSON file with the specific content of a single catalog (.jar file) identified as {name} in the request.

/algorithms

5. GET: Produces a JSON response with the list of available algorithms in all the repository, i.e. in all catalogs of the server.

/algorithms/{name}

6. GET: Responds with a JSON file containing the available information of a specific algorithm identified by {name}.

/reports

7. GET: Obtains the list of all available reports in the server.

/reports/{name}

8. GET: Responds with a JSON file containing the available information of a specific report identified by {name}.

/execution

9. POST: Sends a request for the execution of an algorithm or a report consuming a JSON file. It produces a JSON file as response in case of an algorithm execution or a TEXT/HTML file in case of a report execution. Note that although this resource, with its associated POST method, aims to obtain an optimization service by requesting the execution of an algorithm/report at the server based on a given network state. Although this could be seen as a “get-oriented” or even a remote procedure call approach, we decided to implement a POST method to maintain compatibility with the remainder resources and methods of the interface.

C. Net2Plan OaaS JAVA Client Implementation

The developed OaaS JAVA-based client [17] comprises nine methods corresponding to each combination of resource and method listed in the previous subsection. Each method performs a four-step procedure. First, in case of POST requests to be sent to the server, the information contained in the method’s input parameters is pre-processed and converted into a JSON. Particularly, in the case of the **execution** resource, this step converts into a JSON the network status representation captured in the native Net2Plan .n2p XML-based files. Second, the end-point / resource is defined. Third, the request is sent to the server. Finally, the client retrieves the response of the server. This sequence of steps can be implemented in other

Fig. 2. OaaS hierarchy of resources and associated methods that compose the API definition.

programming languages, opening the door to OaaS applicability in other scenarios and SDN/NFV architectures discussed in the following.

Our implemented JAVA-based client is integrated in the Net2Plan GUI, to allow the interaction with the OaaS server in a visual environment while employing all methods of the built-in Net2Plan network design callback. This integration is further explained in the Section IV.A (see Figs. 4 (b) (c)).

IV. USING NET2PLAN FOR OaaS

In this section, we first describe the workflow of the proposed Network OaaS framework. Subsequently, we illustrate the OaaS usage with the execution of a particular built-in algorithm in Net2Plan. Then we discuss the benefits of enabling network optimization as a service through a REST-based API, which opens the door to SDN/NFV architectures in which network optimization could now be remotely executed by a third-party OaaS server.

A. OaaS Workflow

Fig. 3 illustrates the Net2plan-based OaaS workflow with the sequence in which the methods listed in Section III.B should be used. The workflow begins with (1) the user authentication with a JSON file sent to the server containing the username and password. On the server side, a verification procedure checks whether that credential (i.e. user-password combination) is contained in the oas_users.xml file. In case the combination is present, the server generates a token for the session of the user which is sent to the client within the JSON response; otherwise, an “unauthorized” message is responded to the client. This permits making use of network optimization algorithms by users with the appropriate permissions.

The remainder methods are devoted to the information exchange relevant for the network optimization purposes. Specifically, in (2) a client should upload a catalog implemented as a .jar file. Note that this step can be iteratively executed for uploading multiple catalogs. Then, a set of methods permit the client/user to retrieve information regarding (3) all available catalogs, (4) the specific algorithms and

Fig. 4. Sequence diagram of our proposed OaaS framework.

reports contained in each of them, (5)/(7) all available algorithms / reports available in the repository which may be contained in multiple JAR files and (6)/(8) the specific information of an algorithm/report. Finally, (9) the execution of an algorithm/report can be requested by the client providing within the POST request all the input information required by the algorithm and a topology status represented as .n2p file, which is automatically translated into JSON format in our proposed JAVA-based client implementation. The response to the execution command can be either a JSON file as response in case of an algorithm execution so that a network status is contained within it, or a TEXT/HTML file in case of a report execution given that reports do not modify the network status by only analyze them and generate a human-readable output.

Although the workflow shown in Fig. 3 assumes a client performing both upload catalog and optimization execution operations, other approaches are not excluded. For instance, a given client could be exclusively devoted to development, production and disposal of optimization algorithms while other clients would be only permitted to request the execution of the available optimization services. Moreover, another scenario

could be characterized by the deployment of the catalog by the owner of the OaaS server limiting all clients' role as consumers of the algorithms and reports available in the repository.

B. Example of OaaS Using a Built-in Net2Plan Algorithm

All the resources currently available with Net2Plan as "built-in" algorithms can be incorporated to the proposed OaaS approach. In fact, it is possible to create a large repository with currently available optimization algorithms that include: IGP weights optimization, algorithms usable for MPLS tunnels traffic engineering, Routing Spectrum and Modulation Assignment, among others described in [19].

Fig. 4 exemplifies the usage of an OaaS client-server interaction considering the application of a "flow assignment, open shortest path first weight optimization (greedy heuristic)" algorithm in a 7-node IP-over-WDM Spanish network topology. In particular, Fig. 4(a) shows the Net2Plan GUI containing the canvas with the input network design. Fig. 4(b) shows the offline algorithms tab selecting the referred algorithm in remote mode (employing OaaS) jointly employing Fig. 4(c) remote log-in credentials. The execution of the algorithm generates a JSON message illustrated in Fig. 5(a) that contains the network status as netPlan hierarchy inside the JSON. In particular, several network status aspects can be observed, such as layers, demands, nodes, shared risk groups (srg), etc. Additionally, the input parameters required for executing the algorithm are contained in the bottom part of the JSON in Fig. 5(a). In this particular case, an empty set of parameters is sent by the client because the default set of input parameters were chosen and that information is already available in the server.

Upon the algorithm execution, the JSON shown in Fig. 5(b) is generated, which then in our client implementation and integration in the Net2Plan GUI is represented as output network design (d) and its associated (e) output execution message.

C. Insights and OaaS Potential Applications / Architectures

OaaS permits the execution of a large repository of algorithms and reports exploiting the REST-based API from a variety of programs and applications in multiple scenarios.

Fig. 3. Use-case example of 7-node IP-over-WDM network topology. (a) Input network design, (b) offline algorithms tab in remote mode selecting "flow assignment, open shortest path first weight optimization (greedy heuristic)" algorithm, (c) remote log-in credentials, (d) output network design and (e) output execution message.

Fig. 5. JSON messages generated as algorithm execution (a) request and (b) response.

An illustrative example is shown in Fig. 6, where an NVF orchestrator (NFV-O) and a transport network SDN controller (SDN-C) include an internal module to request optimization services to the OaaS server. This approach permits controllers, managers and orchestrators (e.g. ONOS, OpenStack, OSM) evolve from a reactive role in which a Net2Plan instance instructs their operations [20] toward proactive behaviors in which they request optimization services to a Net2Plan-based OaaS server with an internal OaaS client. A clear example is a potential ONOS (JAVA-based) application requesting OaaS to overcome its internal controller limitations on algorithmic optimization for optical/physical layer performance calculation [21]. Consequently, those OaaS clients requesting for an optimization technique execution from their internal architectural framework/domain can exploit large amount of resources available in a HPC server, which could be potentially hosted in the cloud. In turn, this approach fosters the business model in which, on the one hand, holders of network infrastructures may request the resolution of an optimization problem through the execution of an algorithmic technique while, on the other hand, third-party players can focus on developing and provisioning optimization algorithms.

V. SUMMARY

In this paper, we presented an open-source network OaaS framework based on the Net2Plan network planning tool comprising client, server and its interconnection through a REST-based API. The set of REST resources and associated methods were described including the suggested workflow to populate and use the optimization repository (composed of algorithms and reports). OaaS implementation was reported including a client integration into Net2Plan's GUI illustrating an optimization example of an IP-over-WDM network topology. The proposed network OaaS framework represents a novel approach that enables the usage of optimization services suitable for operationally-complex SDN/NFV carrier-grade transport infrastructure.

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Fig. 6. Potential usage of network OaaS in SDN/NFV ecosystems.

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